

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2026-YIL
IYUN/6-SON, I-QISM

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari

08.00.00 - Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB™
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL STANDARD SERIAL NUMBER INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА LIBRARY.RU

ISSN: 3060-463X

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 2026-yil, iyun.

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afarovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

Yusupov Maxamadamin Abduxamidovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor

Kalonova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor.

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Norboyev Odil Abrayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Pardaev Umidjon Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc)

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA KORPORATIV MENEJMENTNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI VA STRATEGIK AHAMIYATI.....	14
Xabibullayev Dadajon Ro‘ziboyevich	
GREEN ECONOMY TRANSITION AND INVESTMENT CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES	20
Ismoilov Sulaymon Axmadjon o‘g‘li	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL SOLIQQA TORTISH TIZIMINI MUAMMOLAR, YECHIM VA IMKONIYATLARI ASOSIDA JORIY ETISH.....	24
Abdumannobova Gulnoz Akmaljon qizi	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOY TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA INVESTITSIYAVIY JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO‘LLARI	30
Nosirova Kamola Alimovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION MODELLARI VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGINI TAHLIL QILISH	39
Xazratov Abror Panjiyevich	
MINTAQA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY O‘SISHGA TA‘SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	44
Astanayev Kulmaxammat Sanayevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INNOVATSION DEPOZIT XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA UNING BANK RESURS BAZASIGA TA‘SIRI.....	51
Ro‘zimurodov Olim, Normamatov Ruslanbek Shamsiddin o‘g‘li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SUG‘URTA EKOTIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY ASOSLARI.....	57
Xalikulova Gulzada Tadjimuratovna, Kodirova Samira Kamol qizi	
MEHNAT SHARTNOMASI ASOSIDA FAOLIYAT YURITUVCHI QO‘RIQLASH DEPARTAMENTI TIZIMIDAGI IDORAVIY HARBIYLASHTIRILGAN QO‘RIQLASH VA IDORAVIY QOROVULLIK BO‘LINMALARI ISHCHI-XIZMATCHILARIGA DAVLAT IJTIMOY SUG‘URTASINI TATBIQ ETISHNING HUQUQIY-IQTISODIY JIHATLARI	64
Salimbayev Mirsohibjon Mirsodiq o‘g‘li	
ТЕОРИЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ИСЛАМСКОГО СТРАХОВАНИЯ И ЕГО СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ НА ПРИМЕРЕ БЛИЖНЕВОСТОЧНЫХ СТРАН.....	70
Гаффоров Шухрат Насриевич	
IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MADANIY TURIZM SOHASIDAGI SUBYEKTLAR TA‘SIRINI BAHOLASH USULLARI.....	77
Shohruzbek Ruziyev	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”GA O‘TISH SIYOSATINING DASTAKLARI.....	84
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi, Uchqun Yunusovich O‘roqov	
RAQAMLI MEDIA BOZORI SHAROITIDA OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARI KORXONALARIDA DAROMAD MANBALARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING IQTISODIY USTUVOR YO‘NALISHLARI.....	87
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING AHOLINING HUDUDIY XARID QOBILYATIGA YO‘NALTIRILGAN KREDIT SIYOSATINI TASHKIL ETISH TIZIMI	92
Tursunov Bekmuxammad Omonovich, Qarshiyev O‘ktam G‘aybullo o‘g‘li	
INVESTITSIYALAR BUXGALTERIYA HISOBİ OBYEKTI SIFATIDA.....	99
I.Boymurodov	
TA‘LIM MUASSASALARIDA SAMARALI MENEJMENT MEXANIZMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	103
Makhmudov Sunnatjon Abdujabbor o‘g‘li, Ashurova Jasmina Jo‘ra qizi	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA SOG‘LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY ASOSLARI VA BUDJET XARAJATLARI DINAMIKASI	110
Sarsenbaev Baxitjan, Toremuratova Indira, Xayirbaeva Balzira	

TASHQI SAVDO FAOLIYATINI SOLIQQA TORTISH AMALIYOTINING FISKAL VA INSTITUTSIONAL TAHLILI	115
Almuradov Ne'mat Abdullayevich	
SIRKULYAR IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARINI ISLOH QILISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	123
Kuzieva Nargiza Ramazanovna	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA DAVLAT MULKINI BOSHQARISH VA XUSUSIYLASHTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY TAMOYILLARI.....	130
Musurmonqulov Muhammad Ural o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI ISHLAB CHIQRISH TARMOQLARIDA SANOAT 4.0 MODELIDAN FOYDALANISH AMALIYOTI TAHLILI.....	136
Komilova Dilafruz Rustam qizi	
"O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AJNING SINGULYAR VA AMALIY IQTISODIYOTNING INTEGRATSION MEXANIZMI ASOSIDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	141
Bobojonova Zarnigor Shokirovna	
EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHDA INVESTITSİYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	149
Axmedov Umidjon	
NMSH TURIDAGI RELELARNING TEXNIK TAVSIFLARINI TEKSHIRISH UCHUN STEND ISHLAB CHIQISH.	156
Raxmonov Bobomurod, Qodirov Azamat, Yusupova Shirin, Mirzaraxmedov Zafar	
ТЕОРЕТИКО-МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ОЦЕНКЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ КЛАСТЕРОВ ИНДУСТРИИ РАЗВЛЕЧЕНИЙ НА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ (ЗАНЯТОСТЬ, ДОХОДЫ, ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТОК, НАЛОГОВЫЕ ПОСТУПЛЕНИЯ): КРИТЕРИИ И МЕТОДЫ ОЦЕНКИ	163
Султонмуродов Мирзо-Улугбек Мукумжон углы	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ В ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕНТРАХ: ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ AI-ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ДЛЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ УЧЕБНЫХ ГРУПП.....	170
Джамолова Хилола Исматиллаевна, Алимова Машхура Тоирхоновна	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI	175
Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLARINING RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	181
Raxmanov Zafar Yashinovich	
КРЕАТИВНЫЙ ТУРИЗМ КАК ФАКТОР РАЗВИТИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ РЕМЕСЕЛ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	187
Хушназарова Махзуна Гуламджановна	
MADANIY MEROS OBYEKTLARINING XALQARO TURIZM OQIMLARIGA TA'SIRI: GLOBAL TENDENSIYALAR VA MINTAQAVIY TAHLIL	193
Qilichov Muhridin Husniddin o'g'li	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ И НАКОПЛЕНИЕ ПЕРВЫХ МЕДИЦИНСКИХ ЗНАНИЙ	200
Рахматуллаева Фотима Султонмуродовна	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA SEGMENTLARNI HISOB OBYEKTI SIFATIDA TASNIFLASHNING USLUBIY ASOSLARI	206
Bobomuradova Sarvinoz Ziyadullayevna	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA SEGMENTLARNI HISOB OBYEKTI SIFATIDA TASNIFLASHNING USLUBIY ASOSLARI	206
Bobomuradova Sarvinoz Ziyadullayevna	
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ НИТРООКСИДИРОВАНИЯ НА СТРУКТУРУ И ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИОННЫЕ СВОЙСТВА КОНСТРУКЦИОННЫХ СТАЛЕЙ	212
Бойназаров Урол Равшанович	

SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHI VA IQTISODIY O'SISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING TA'SIRI	219
Pardayev Orifjon Charshamiyevich	
IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA FISKAL INSTRUMENTLAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING AMALIY JIHLTLARI	224
Mardonov Kamoliddin Karamiddinovich	
RAQAMLI TAFOVUT (DIGITAL DIVIDE) VA UNING QISHLOQ HUDUDLARIDA ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRI (ISH KUCHI VA KAPITAL HAQIDAGI IQTISODIY NAZARIYA DOIRASIDA)	230
O'rozaliyev Elyor Shuxrat o'g'li	
THE ESSENCE AND PLACE OF LOGISTICS IN THE SYSTEM OF THE NEW MARKET ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN	236
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	

THE ESSENCE AND PLACE OF LOGISTICS IN THE SYSTEM OF THE NEW MARKET ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna

Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

E-mail: musaeva_shoira@mail.ru

ORCID: 0009-0000-9577-6976

Abstract. The article examines the development of logistics systems, their potential, and the expansion of commodity markets, which have increased scientific interest in this field and contributed to the enhancement of the essence, objectives, and priorities of interregional economic cooperation. The opportunities and development prospects of logistics companies were analyzed, and practical recommendations for their further improvement were proposed. The impact of logistics system development on strengthening the competitiveness of territories was also studied.

Keywords: logistics, regional competitiveness, logistics potential, territory, transport infrastructure.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada logistika tizimlarini rivojlantirish, ularning salohiyatini oshirish va tovar bozorlarini kengaytirish masalalari yoritilib, ushbu sohaga bo'lgan ilmiy qiziqishning ortishi hamda mintaqalararo iqtisodiy hamkorlikning mohiyati, maqsadlari va ustuvor yo'nalishlarining takomillashuviga ta'siri ko'rib chiqilgan. Logistika kompaniyalarining rivojlanish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinib, ularning faoliyat samaradorligini yanada oshirish bo'yicha amaliy takliflar ishlab chiqilgan. Shuningdek, logistika tizimlarining rivojlanishi hududlar raqobatbardoshligini mustahkamlashdagi ahamiyati o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: logistika, mintaqaning raqobatbardoshligi, logistika salohiyati, hudud, transport infratuzilmasi.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены вопросы развития логистических систем, повышения их потенциала и расширения товарных рынков, что способствует росту научного интереса к данной сфере и совершенствованию сущности, целей и приоритетов межрегионального экономического сотрудничества. Проанализированы перспективы развития логистических компаний и предложены практические рекомендации по дальнейшему повышению эффективности их деятельности. Изучено влияние развития логистических систем на укрепление конкурентоспособности регионов.

Ключевые слова: логистика, конкурентоспособность региона, логистический потенциал, регион, транспортная инфраструктура.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the relatively recent emergence of the term logistics, this concept has been interpreted in various ways. As an economic activity, logistics has dozens of definitions in the scientific literature. In its broadest sense, logistics is understood as the management of all types of flows existing in economic systems, including material, human, energy, financial, and information flows.

According to the definition provided in modern economic dictionaries, logistics is a branch of economic science whose subject is the organization and regulation of the processes involved in moving goods from producers to consumers, managing inventories, and developing the infrastructure necessary for commodity exchange.

Both domestic and foreign economic literature offer broader interpretations of logistics, where the object of management is not limited to material flows. Today, logistics encompasses the management of human, energy, financial, information, and other flows occurring within economic systems. As a result, concepts such as banking logistics, information logistics, and service logistics have emerged. In this context, logistics is regarded as an interdisciplinary scientific field focused on identifying new opportunities to enhance the efficiency of material and related flows within economic systems.

To further clarify the concept of logistics, it is useful to consider it from both economic and managerial perspectives. As a scientific discipline, logistics develops theoretical principles, methods, and mathematical models that facilitate the planning, coordination, control, and management of transportation, storage, and other material and intangible operations throughout the following processes:

- delivery of raw materials and supplies to production enterprises;
- processing of raw materials, materials, and semi-finished products;
- delivery of finished products to consumers in accordance with their requirements;
- transmission, storage, and processing of relevant information.

In the context of the evolving global economy, improving the conditions for the effective implementation of logistics processes has become increasingly important. At the same time, the study of factors contributing to regional competitiveness is gaining greater significance. Under modern market conditions, enhancing regional competitiveness is closely associated with improving product quality, increasing the efficiency of logistics services, introducing innovative technologies, optimizing operational costs, and expanding the application of resource- and energy-efficient solutions. These measures contribute to sustainable economic development and strengthen the competitive position of regions in national and international markets.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing scientific foundations, including the theories of general economic equilibrium, reproduction, international trade, and economic integration, have provided a solid basis for studying the conditions and factors influencing the formation and development of the potential of regional logistics systems as an important direction for enhancing regional competitiveness.

The theory of general economic equilibrium, proposed by the founder of modern economic modeling, Léon Walras, considers the economy as a system comprising two interconnected groups: owners of production factors and entrepreneurs engaged in socio-economic interactions and relationships. This approach highlights the importance of balanced economic development and effective resource allocation within a unified economic space.

From the perspective of regional potential development, the equilibrium state of markets reflects the interdependence of market prices and economic activities under conditions of limited resources. The study of various interpretations of reproduction theory has made it possible to identify a key principle: sustainable economic development requires a balanced relationship among sectors and industries within the economy, creating favorable conditions for expanded reproduction and long-term growth.

Modern theories of economic growth are largely based on the principles of reproduction theory and have been further developed through the contributions of economists such as R. Harrod, E. Domar, R. Solow, and J. Hicks. These theoretical approaches provide valuable analytical tools for modeling the functioning of market systems under conditions of sustainable economic growth and for identifying opportunities to strengthen their competitiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking techniques, and digital metrics to achieve its objectives. Data collection and analysis were conducted using comprehensive monitoring methods applied to digital and social media platforms. These methods facilitated the identification of current trends, the assessment of logistics development factors, and the evaluation of their contribution to regional competitiveness.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The theory of international trade provides a clear understanding of the factors determining the direction of foreign trade flows. The study of logistics potential demonstrates that the development of a country's areas of specialization contributes to strengthening regional competitiveness, improving the well-being of the population, enhancing productivity, and increasing the production of competitive goods and services.

Based on the fundamental principles of international trade theory and taking into account the successful experience of European integration models, particularly the European Union, integration processes are currently expanding across various countries and regions. The broadening scope of international economic integration has not only transformed its characteristics but has also shaped its key directions of development, including the establishment of free economic zones and free trade areas, the formation of customs and economic unions, the simplification of cross-border trade procedures, and the promotion of the free movement of capital and labor.

Drawing upon existing theories and generally accepted economic principles, the logistics potential of a region can be considered an important object of research because it plays a significant role in regional

development and competitiveness. At the same time, regional logistics potential requires practical assessment approaches that take into account the specific characteristics and development conditions of individual regions.

The flows within a regional logistics system, including their intensity, direction, structure, and level of integration, are key factors determining the logistics potential of a region. The study of logistics potential makes it possible to identify the factors influencing logistics flows and to evaluate their contribution to regional development. Furthermore, the efficient movement of material and related flows depends on the quality of interaction among the elements of the regional logistics system and the effectiveness of the connections established between them.

The logistics potential of a region consists of several interrelated components, including transport, infrastructure, customs, human resources, and other regional systems. Together, these components characterize not only the logistics infrastructure and market participants operating within the region but also the quality, efficiency, and development level of logistics processes.

The evolution of the concept of “logistics potential” demonstrates its growing importance in economic research. Initially, logistics potential was primarily examined at the enterprise level through qualitative and quantitative indicators. Subsequently, this concept was extended to the assessment of regions and national economies. During the early 1970s, research on logistics potential focused on identifying opportunities for economic efficiency through the creation of integrated systems for managing material resources and optimizing their structure and utilization. Over time, increasing attention has been devoted to the role of logistics potential in supporting sustainable development and enhancing regional competitiveness.

Further research into the conditions that facilitate the formation of competitive advantages for enterprises and regions highlights the importance of identifying and evaluating the factors that contribute to the development of regional logistics potential.

International and interregional cooperation, viewed as long-term economic relations among economic entities from different countries and regions, creates favorable opportunities for strengthening regional economic systems. Researchers emphasize that scientifically grounded diversification and specialization of production contribute to improving economic efficiency and enhancing regional competitiveness. In addition, the effective management of logistics flows allows regions to make better use of their available resources and development opportunities.

These considerations form an important theoretical and methodological foundation for studying the principles, factors, and mechanisms of regional logistics potential development, as well as for its comprehensive analysis and evaluation.

The study of regional logistics potential was carried out through the analysis of cause-and-effect relationships that make it possible to identify the interaction between logistics potential and the factors influencing its formation, including geopolitical, economic, social, and methodological factors. At the same time, modern logistics practices and current global economic trends provide opportunities to assess the logistics potential of a region as an integrated set of capabilities within the logistics management system of the territory under consideration.

This approach highlights the importance of evaluating logistics potential in order to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the current state and future development prospects of a particular region. By designing a system of relevant indicators and factors, it becomes possible to identify development opportunities and determine strategic priorities for strengthening regional logistics potential.

In many studies that examine regional potential from a logistics perspective, the primary assessment indicators are freight turnover and transport turnover, calculated by aggregating transportation volumes within the region. While these indicators provide valuable information regarding the activities of regional enterprises, a more comprehensive assessment can be achieved by additionally considering the volume of transit flows. Furthermore, indicators such as transportation costs, delivery distances, route efficiency, and infrastructure quality contribute to a more complete evaluation of logistics performance.

Logistics potential can be defined as an integrated characteristic of a logistics system that reflects its capacity to perform logistics functions under specific external environmental conditions. Since logistics systems develop through the interaction of factors operating at the micro-, meso-, and macro-logistics levels, it is important to consider both the quantitative and qualitative relationships among system elements.

At the micro level, the enterprise logistics system generates and manages material, financial, and information flows. The logistics potential at this level consists of elements of the internal organizational environment and is influenced by factors associated with the organization's immediate external environment.

At the meso level, the logistics system represents a network of enterprises and organizations that facilitates the formation and management of regional and interregional economic flows. These flows include material resources, commodities, financial resources, information, labor, energy, and other related flows, all of which contribute to achieving regional development objectives.

Accordingly, the logistics potential of a region encompasses a broad combination of interconnected components, including geographical, transport, transit, human resource, warehouse infrastructure, customs, information, and communication potentials. Each component is formed and developed under the influence of a corresponding group of factors and contributes to the overall effectiveness of the regional logistics system.

At the macro level, the logistics system represents a large-scale material flow management network that includes regional production complexes, international corporations, financial-industrial groups, and national economies. It integrates infrastructure systems as well as interstate and global economic flows. The logistics potential at this level reflects the capabilities and resources of international logistics networks to enhance efficiency, optimize logistics operations, and support sustainable economic development on a global scale.

Studying the content of the concept of “**logistics potential**” made it possible to identify several approaches to defining this category.

1. Logistics potential as a set of available resources and capabilities:

- Logistics potential is viewed as a system of commodity exchange and interaction among organizations within a region. This approach emphasizes the value component of logistics activities and highlights their contribution to regional economic development.
- Logistics potential is defined as a combination of factors that support the achievement of an organization's strategic development objectives.
- The potential of a logistics system is considered as an integrated set of material and information flows, with particular emphasis on the economic and managerial aspects of logistics processes.
- Logistics potential is associated with opportunities to enhance efficiency through the effective management of logistics infrastructure. In this regard, logistics infrastructure is regarded as an important component of the broader infrastructure system of territorial entities and, ultimately, the national economy.
- Logistics potential is represented as a combination of elements, methods, tools, and environmental factors that enable logistics systems to effectively support the development strategies of firms and regions.

2. Logistics potential as the result and capability of logistics system performance:

- Logistics potential is considered the ability of a developed transport infrastructure to support extensive international transport connections while ensuring efficient methods of freight and passenger transportation.
- Logistics potential is also associated with the outcomes of innovative activities undertaken by economic entities operating within regional logistics systems.
- Cluster structures are viewed as an effective mechanism for strengthening logistics potential by enhancing the participation of enterprises in regional and interregional economic relations and supporting long-term development strategies.
- International experts assess logistics potential using widely recognized indicators that reflect the effectiveness of logistics processes and the overall performance of national logistics systems.
- Logistics potential is interpreted as the capacity of a region to carry out logistics activities efficiently while making effective use of available resources. In this context, the continuous identification of development opportunities and the implementation of improvement measures contribute to strengthening regional logistics performance.

The scientific approaches discussed above reflect different classification features of logistics potential. The resource-based approach focuses primarily on quantitative characteristics, whereas the efficiency-based approach emphasizes qualitative aspects. At the same time, one of the most important characteristics of logistics potential is the ability of the participants in a regional logistics system to achieve common goals through cooperation, coordination, and the strengthening of territorial competitiveness.

In a broad sense, the logistics potential of a region can be defined as the ability and capacity of regional logistics infrastructure and market participants to effectively implement logistics processes while adapting to changing environmental conditions and utilizing available development opportunities. This potential is influenced by several factors, including the level of development of the logistics services market, the quality of transport infrastructure, the advancement of information and communication systems, and the scientific and human resource potential of the region.

Since the interaction of the elements of regional logistics potential creates new opportunities and a higher level of system effectiveness, it is possible to emphasize the significant contribution of logistics systems to regional competitiveness. This interaction is based on the unique characteristics and complementary roles of the structural elements of logistics potential, which together create favorable conditions for sustainable economic growth and regional development.

Accordingly, the logistics potential of a region may be defined as an integrated system of resources, capabilities, infrastructure, and institutional conditions that enable logistics market participants to efficiently organize and manage logistics processes, strengthen regional competitiveness, and support long-term socio-

economic development.

The logistics potential of a region can be defined as a combination of existing, developed, and prospective opportunities that enable the creation and effective management of logistics systems and the efficient coordination of material and related flows. These opportunities contribute to strengthening regional economic development and enhancing competitiveness.

This definition highlights the key characteristic of regional logistics potential—the effective utilization of the opportunities created by regional logistics systems. The potential of a logistics system reflects the integrated and interconnected nature of its subsystems, which collectively contribute to improving the economic performance of the region and strengthening its competitive position. Through the efficient interaction of these subsystems, logistics potential serves as an important driver of sustainable regional development and long-term economic growth.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the integration of economic processes creates favorable conditions for the effective implementation of logistics management concepts and emphasizes the growing importance of developing regional logistics potential. The formation of a regional logistics development strategy should be based on a comprehensive methodology that takes into account the socio-economic characteristics of the region, the distribution of productive forces, and long-term development priorities. Such an approach contributes to the efficient use of regional resources, supports sustainable economic growth, and strengthens regional competitiveness. The assessment of logistics potential should be carried out with consideration of the development of international transit corridors, the economic advantages of multimodal transportation, and the identification of efficient solutions for the operation of regional transport systems. The strengthening of integrated logistics systems and the expansion of the logistics services market create additional opportunities for specialized companies to improve service quality, increase operational efficiency, and enhance their contribution to regional economic development. In the future, the implementation of a diversified logistics development strategy will support the modernization of logistics services, facilitate the introduction of advanced technologies and innovative solutions into business activities, strengthen transport, information, and logistics infrastructure, and expand the role of logistics at local, regional, and national levels. Furthermore, the development of logistics potential will promote successful integration into international logistics networks and global markets. The consistent implementation of these measures will improve the efficiency of logistics systems, create new opportunities for economic cooperation, support sustainable regional development, and strengthen the competitive position of regions in both national and international economies.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Adopted on April 30, 2023.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017, “On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. <https://www.lex.uz/docs/-3107036?otherlang=1>
3. Orlov, S.V. Territorial Organization of the Transport Complex: The Transport Cluster as a Form of Organization. Modern Technologies. System Analysis and Modeling, No. 2 (38), 2013.
4. Karrieva, Y., Nematov, K., & Masharipov, A. International Logistics: Textbook. Tashkent, 2009.
5. Tairova, M.M., Abdulloev, A.J. Logistics: Textbook. Bukhara: Sadridin Salim Bukhariy Publishing House, 2020. – 128 p.
6. Musaeva, Sh.A. Customs Work and Security: Textbook. Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service. Samarkand: STEP-SEL LLC Publishing House, 2025.

muhandislik

& iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Abdurahmon Qurbonov

2026. № 6

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100